

UNHEALTHY FAMILY ENVIRONMENT AND ITS CAUSES

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Annotation :Mediation is a specific type of activity of social importance and is an active relationship formed on the basis of recognition of basic freedoms. This article talks about the formation and development of tolerant attitude in resolving conflicts among students.

Key word: Meditation, xenophobia, society, conflictology, psychology, antic, method.

The health of the family environment is the first factor in the formation of a child's behavior. As we know, the family environment: parents and their relationship with the child, family peace, mutual trust and respect of adults for each other are important in the formation of a child's behavior. On the contrary, disagreements, conflicts, and inappropriate behavior of parents and adults in the family cannot but negatively affect the child's behavior. Young children brought up in families with constant quarrels and conflicts are afraid and tearful. Later, some of these children show indifference, helplessness, and lack of independent thinking, while others constantly consider themselves unnecessary to others, are shy, unable to adapt, and their sociability decreases. After all, in an unhealthy family, the main focus is on the conflicts between the parents. Child rearing is often neglected by them[105;1]. There are families where parents sometimes take all their pain out on their children. That is, it can be anger, threats, and physical punishment of the child. In short, the child becomes a victim of parental quarrels. In turn, such actions pave the way for the formation of aggressive behavior in children.

Lack of knowledge of child psychology, physiology, and pedagogy among parents. Unfortunately, according to our observations, some parents, especially

young parents, lack knowledge of child physiology, psychology, and upbringing. Therefore, they cannot understand the reason for the negative changes in their child's behavior. For example, a child's capriciousness or stubbornness may be due to some disease or a problem in his physical development. In some cases, children's chronic illnesses also cause them to be capricious and stubborn. Often, such children are pampered by adults in the family. As a result, they develop a certain egoism. In turn, the unhealthy physiological state of the child negatively affects his psyche, including intuition, perception, memory, attention, and thinking. Therefore, parents should be extremely attentive to their children.

Improper organization of the child's daily routine. Improper organization of the child's daily routine leads to negative changes in his behavior. Because the child's daily routine necessarily includes activities such as rest, eating, self-service, participation in classes, sports, and playing games. We know that children raised in preschool educational organizations adhere to the daily routine. However, parents of children raised in the family pay little attention to this issue. Especially in recent years, due to such a negative situation, many children have forgotten what a valuable resource is called time. The fact that such children spend hours and days playing on TV or the phone is a clear proof of our opinion. The lives of such children are chaotic, they do not rest on time and do not eat on time. Later, due to the development of various diseases in such children, they often suffer from anemia, fatigue, a feeling of dissatisfaction with themselves, and gastrointestinal diseases.

Therefore, the earlier we, educators, start teaching children to follow a daily routine, the faster and easier we will achieve our goal. Children develop a habit of following a daily routine. Due to the sequential execution of rest, participation in classes, completing assignments, meals, sports and other activities in a certain order, the child's daily routine is rationally distributed. Completing all the tasks specified in the daily routine on time ensures that the child does not get tired and is always healthy and energetic.

Unfortunately, such a negative situation as a constant violation of the daily routine cannot but affect not only the child's spiritual and mental state, but also his physical development. Such children are weak-willed, impatient, and do not strive for goals in life, and are surrounded by vices such as risk-taking, laziness, and idleness. A child who follows a routine will grow up to be someone who does everything according to a plan, is meticulous, does not get discouraged in the face of difficulties, is patient, has a strong will, and most importantly, does not waste time on useless things.

Feedback Unplanned childbearing in the family. In today's culture and every family that strives to be at a high level of spirituality, it is necessary to plan for having children. The interval between the birth of children should be 3-5 years. However, most Uzbek families do not pay attention to this ratio. As a result, the age between children is 1-2 years. It goes without saying that this situation creates a number of problems in the family. That is, as a result of pregnancy before the mother's body has fully recovered, the mother develops various diseases, anemia, iodine deficiency, nervous disorders, and other manifestations of deterioration in health. In turn, such diseases and pathological conditions have a negative impact on the development of the fetus. That is, a number of diseases are also observed in the born child. Due to illnesses, children become capricious, tearful, and stubborn. These situations are considered complex psychological processes for the family, and the mother suffers the most. Due to the mother's restlessness and inability to eat on time, she is also nervous. Due to the mother's impatience, irritability, anger, and frustration, problems arise in raising a child. The mother does not have enough time to deal with the first child separately, and the questions of the child who is just beginning to understand the world remain unanswered. Thus, the formation of the child's personality and the enrichment of his worldview develop slowly. Family upbringing is a type of social upbringing, in which all members of the family actively participate in it, teaching each other their knowledge and experience. Family upbringing is a lifelong process. No other social institution can match the

love of filial piety, brotherhood, and sisterhood that is formed in the family. These feelings, being a high moral wealth in themselves, serve as a solid foundation for a person's social relations and the assimilation of the morality of society. National family relations based on equality, friendship, and mutual respect of family members serve as an important school for the formation of moral norms of male and female relations in young people, and for the upbringing of practical skills and qualities necessary for future family life.

Difficult course of the adaptive process in a child towards any community. A child experiences an adaptive process several times throughout his life. As the scientist N. Egamberdiyeva noted, "The birth of a person is the first test of adaptation. Even a newborn baby has adaptation mechanisms"[84;2]. It is during this adaptation process that various problems occur in children. That is, the child is observed to be capricious, capricious, rude, and inhuman. Unfortunately, these negative traits, if not prevented in time, can later become embedded in the child's character and make it difficult for him to adapt to any team. Such children have very few friends, or even none at all. Their character is characterized by negative traits such as constant dissatisfaction with something, dissatisfaction with oneself, disobedience, and hesitation. In particular, it can be seen that the adaptation process in such children is prolonged for a long time. The main reason for these negative aspects is related to the child's temperament, individuality, excessive upbringing, and other aspects.

Adaptation of preschool children is formed more on the basis of adults and their own experience. It is precisely because of the impatience or rudeness of adults during this adaptation process that a child experiences a crisis period. This is especially observed during the adaptation of children to preschool educational organizations. One of the main reasons for this is that the child is very attached to the mother. This process has a very strong impact on the child's psyche. He feels like he is surrounded by absolute "strangers". Constant crying, refusal to eat, rudeness towards peers, insomnia are observed. As a result, not only the child's

mental, but also physical health is damaged [70;3]. For this reason, it is important to be extremely careful with the child during the crisis period.

The negative impact of the media. The media is the most powerful tool that affects the psyche and upbringing of children today. Television and mobile communication devices are in the lead in this regard. Through these means, children get acquainted with information that does not correspond to their age and worldview. In particular, various militant films and cartoons shown on television lead to the formation of negative changes in children's behavior. Also, most of the various games loaded on mobile devices have a negative impact on the psyche of children. Unfortunately, today, parents are putting phones in the hands of children even in infancy. Although various noisy sounds and extreme speed of movements attract the attention of children, they cannot but negatively affect the psyche of a young child. In such cases, sleep disorders, decreased appetite, irritability, capriciousness, laziness are observed in young children. In recent years, especially in children under one year old, a situation of addiction to the phone has become noticeable. So, if you take the phone from the hands of children, they start screaming and crying at the top of their voices. This is explained by the manifestation of an aggressive state in them. Or, in order to comfort a baby who does not yet understand anything, mothers make them sit in front of the TV for hours. As a result, the physical and mental development of the child is impaired, and they develop physical defects such as improper growth of the musculoskeletal system, curvature of the spine, and rickets. At the same time, the normal course of the mental state in children, that is, attention, perception, imagination, memory, etc., is disrupted. As a result, such children are insensitive and unkind to the environment, even to people. The most sad thing is that such children grow up far from reality, they believe that everything in life can be achieved quickly and easily. For this reason, a constant mood of discontent reigns in them. In particular, such children are aggressive, lazy, and belligerent[100;3].

Therefore, the negative impact of the media can be distinguished by the

following aspects.

Feedback The use of very bright colors to attract children's attention. All modern cartoons produced today are made in very bright colors. The colors are so bright that they are far from reality and colorful. This has a negative effect on the psyche of children. That is, later the child wants to see everything in reality in such bright colors, and over time, they become dissatisfied with themselves and others, and aggressive.

Various loud and noisy sounds. Modern cartoons are made with loud, wheezing sounds and noisy voices. Although these sounds and sounds attract children's attention, they cannot but have a negative effect on their psyche, that is, they cause children to be noisy, imitative, and belligerent. Especially in young children, they cause a feeling of fear and anxiety. Many children become afraid of being alone, crybaby.

The plot and content are not suitable for the age and mentality of children. The plot of most cartoons today is very complex and does not suit the age of children at all. At the same time, events in them occur quickly and intensively. As a result, children cannot understand the connection between events and their imagination becomes confused. Most importantly, the educational value of cartoons is gradually decreasing due to the complexity of the plot and content. The child cannot understand the difference between a negative and a positive character. They do not have the ability to evaluate and qualify the behavior of the characters. In particular, due to children watching cartoons that are not suitable for their age, an imbalance occurs in their physical and mental development.

Incorrect approach to child upbringing. According to observations, most families have an incorrect approach to child upbringing. That is, in this case, two completely incompatible approaches to child upbringing can be seen by parents.

1. Parents and adults pampering and pampering the child.
2. Excessive strictness towards the child.

In the first wrong approach, the child is pampered, which leads to the

emergence of negative vices such as selfishness, arrogance, laziness, laziness, impatience. Observations show that the majority of pampered children have more signs of selfishness. This is because the fact that adults create all the attention and conditions for the child and unconditional fulfillment of all the child's wishes and desires is explained by the formation of negative vices in his behavior. As a result, such children have a decrease in positive qualities such as independence, diligence, initiative, responsibility, and hard work. Such children have difficulty finding their place in life, especially in difficult situations in relationships with people. This situation is often found in families raising only one child. Because parents fulfill all their child's desires more and faster than he wants. Thus, the child does not have patience and satisfaction. After the child reaches adulthood, various difficulties and worries await him in life. In this process, the mistake in raising a child manifests itself. Another manifestation of the wrong approach to raising a child is excessive severity towards him. Choosing such a path of upbringing, especially without taking into account the age and psychological aspects of preschool children, is an extremely wrong approach. In such cases, serious problems are observed in the child's psyche. That is, as a result of strong fear or aggression, a violation of the emotional state leads to: excitement, depression, memory loss, speech problems, and a number of similar negative situations. Of course, a violation of the mental state, in turn, also affects the physical development of the child. As a result of fear and aggression, sleep disturbances, decreased appetite, rapid fatigue, and a decrease in the immune system are observed. Fear in children leads to a decrease in their self-confidence, restriction of independent thinking, and difficulty in adapting to any team, while aggression leads to the manifestation of such vices as aggression, quarrelsomeness, and fighting in children. It should be remembered that in the process of developing the child's emotional world, its activity can legitimately increase. Usually, at this necessary stage of psychological correction, carried out with the help of adults, the child can master communication that corresponds to the reality surrounding him. The elimination of child aggression

should begin by identifying its cause. If aggression is not due to a violation of the emotional world, corrective work should be focused not on eliminating it, but on mitigating aggressive behavior that leads to negative consequences and preventing its manifestation. At the same time, adults themselves.

In the West, the authors of a number of scientific studies have set themselves the difficult task of studying the system of family and family relations, factors affecting the upbringing of a child in the comprehensive formation of a child's personality, and have sought to solve such an important and complex pedagogical and psychological social task. In these studies, effective general pedagogical, psychoprophylactic and psychological-pedagogical correction and counseling, parent and child training programs that are applicable in real practical life and everyday activities have been developed and recommended. These proposed programs are used as psycho-pedagogical, methodological assistance for the formation of a child's personality and his place in society.

In Western psycho-pedagogical literature, special attention is paid to issues such as the fact that negative changes in a child's behavior occur due to the improper formation of interpersonal relationships between parents and children, as well as the improper development of interpersonal relationships between children. Also, in this regard, researchers analyzed the causes of such differences by comparing the positive impact of children's interpersonal relationships on the formation and development of the child's personality and the cases in which interpersonal relationships inevitably lead to negative changes in the behavior of children raised outside their own family (in orphanages, close relatives). As a result, it became clear that the correct, sincere and fair organization of interpersonal relationships in children's behavior is of great importance.

The issue of developing positive qualities in a child's behavior was expressed in the studies of the American psychologist R.A.Shpits. R. Spitz, studying the characteristics of a child's behavior in the early stages of a child's birth, emphasizes that the child's positive interaction with his parents and loved ones, the sincere

treatment of parents and loved ones, the attention given to him in the norm, ensure the child's spiritual, physical, and spiritual maturity, the good development of such qualities as enthusiasm, activity, cheerfulness, curiosity, and the child's early acquisition of language and the ability to express his speech fluently. According to the researcher, the main factor in negative changes in the child's behavior is the need to be extremely careful when interacting with him, it is necessary to approach this issue correctly and seriously, otherwise it is necessary to pay attention to the difficulty of achieving the expected result from upbringing. Rene Spitz also notes that children growing up without parental love cannot adequately perceive the events happening around them. This behavior sometimes appears together with autoerotic states and as a result causes negative changes in their behavior. These changes are manifested in the child becoming withdrawn, withdrawing from everyone, being in a depressed mood. Another scientist, Anna Freud, bases the formation of positive traits in the child's behavior on the attention and care shown to children in the family, the richness of emotional experiences of family members, and the need to share the child's feelings. In her opinion, children who grow up in such an environment develop qualities in their character such as loving themselves and those around them, helping them, and enjoying the world around them. Children who grow up without such a positive environment in their family and outside the family behave in a way that contradicts moral standards towards themselves and those around them. An indifferent environment leads to the manifestation of rudeness and aggressiveness in them. This, in turn, leads to the emergence of criminal groups in society, the emergence of various conflicts, and unpleasant incidents in families and institutions. In general, due to the above reasons and factors, there are many problems in children's behavior. This, in turn, imposes a number of tasks on members of society, in particular, educators and psychologists, and parents. In particular, in this regard, it is advisable to further increase the effectiveness of preventive work carried out with the family, and to strengthen the provision of knowledge to parents about the psychology, physiology

and pedagogy of children.

References

1. Kjell L. A. Personality theories: basic principles, research and application: a textbook for universities / L. A. Kjell , D. Ziegler . St. Petersburg: Peter, 1997. 606 p.
2. Shabolina V.V. Psychology of addictive behavior: a pattern of behavior associated with the use of drugs and other psychoactive substances –/ V.V. St. Petersburg: St. Petersburg Publishing House . Univ., 2004. 336 p.
3. Shakurov R. Kh. Causes of conflicts in pedagogical teams –and methods of their elimination / R. Kh., B. S. Alisherov // Issues of psychology. 1986. No. 6. P. 67-76.

